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Active aging and learning outcomes: what can older people learn from participation?

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Abstract

Although the concept of “active aging” has been widely used as a framework to underpin an optimistic view of aging, few studies have focused on the activities it encompasses and what participants learn. The aim of this study was to explore and compare the learning outcomes acquired from different active aging activities. A sample of 448 people aged 60 years and above participated in the study. The vast majority of participants stated that they had learned something valuable from their involvement in the active aging activity. Content analysis showed two main types of learning: self-focused learning and other-focused learning, whose frequency differed depending on the activity in which participants were engaged. The results of this study show the complexity of the concept of active aging and the need to diversify actions to promote each of the activities included in this framework, based on the type of learning acquired.

Keywords: learning; active aging; volunteering; university; leisure; activism

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In recent decades, we have witnessed a growing emphasis on an optimistic approach to later life, which underlines the possibility of aging in a healthy and productive way. While some of the concepts proposed to study aging from this rather optimistic point of view tend to be individualistic and health-oriented (e.g. successful aging, Rowe & Kahn, 2015), others try to combine personal and societal benefits. For instance, active aging has been proposed as a framework to understand how people can 'age well', including both their engagement with society and the characteristics of the context in which they age (WHO, 2002). It has contributed to identify the benefits of activity in later life, both for the individual in terms of health and well-being and for the community in terms of social capital and cohesion. Additionally, it has acted as a guiding principle for the design of social policies to promote forms of aging well (Marsillas et al., 2017).

Nevertheless, the concept of active aging has its limitations (e.g., Sao José, Timonen, Amado, & Santos, 2017). One of the key problems relates to the definition (or lack thereof) of 'activity,' since there is no clarity regarding the type of activities that count as 'active aging' and the level of involvement (if any) required to reap the benefits. Furthermore, there is some uncertainty about whether all the activities included within the concept produce the same benefits in every older person (e.g., Morrow-Howell, Hong, & Tang, 2009). In this respect, while some benefits associated with an active lifestyle in older age have been extensively studied in previous research (e.g. longevity, personal well-being or social capital), others factors, such as older people's perception of what they have learned from their involvement in the activity, have received less attention. In our view, what older people

learn from their activities is key to understanding their commitment to these activities and their interest in continuing their participation in the future.

The objective of the present study was to explore learning outcomes acquired by people who participate in a range of active aging activities.

The diversity of active aging activities

In the empirical study of active aging, one of the first aspects to determine is the range and intensity of activities included in an 'active lifestyle' and whether they have the same value in personal and societal terms. Some authors have underlined the tendency to restrict active aging to certain types of activity, i.e., those with a clear monetary value that contribute to the sustainability of the welfare system (Boudiny, 2013). From that point of view, older people's involvement in the labor market and their participation in physical activities represent paradigmatic examples of active aging, since they help keep pension and healthcare costs down.

However, such a reductionist view excludes many other types of activity that may have an impact on older people's quality of life and well-being. Some leisure activities, particularly those involving a certain amount of physical or intellectual effort (Caro, Caspi, Burr, & Mutchler, 2009), educational activities (Narushima, Liu, & Diestelkamp, 2018), provision of care in family contexts (Baker, Cahalin, Gerst, & Burr, 2005), volunteering (Principi, Jensen, & Lamura, 2014) and political activism (Serrat, Villar, & Celdrán, 2015) are also frequently labeled as active aging activities. Nevertheless, the danger of this extension of the active aging boundary is that these activities are viewed as interchangeable and that their differences with respect to predictors, their meaning and their personal and social impact are overlooked. Classifying them according to a set of criteria could represent

the first step towards systematizing and comparing such a wide range of potential active aging activities. This task is theoretically sound, since it organizes an otherwise fuzzy concept and identifies key activities according to their predictors and outcomes; it also has practical implications, since it allows the promotion of certain activities tailored to different profiles of older people or according to specific desired outcomes.

One of the first criteria that differentiate active aging activities is whether they are self- or other-oriented (Villar & Celdrán, 2012). Thus, in self-oriented activities, the activity implies mainly individual benefits, in terms of health, well-being, self-fulfillment or personal development, but no other people are involved in or affected by the activity. Training courses in which older people participate “for the sake of learning” (Kim & Merriam, 2004) or leisure activities based on cultural enrichment (Cann, 2017) represent good examples of self-oriented active aging activities. In other-oriented activities, meanwhile, the activity is focused on, and contributes to, the development of other people or the community, or of society as a whole. Voluntary programs or political activism are good examples of other-oriented activities. These activities also offer individual benefits, but these benefits are not the main objective of the activity (e.g., Villar, 2012).

A second aspect to consider is the amount of resources needed to engage in the activity (Burr, Mutchler, & Caro, 2007). Thus, some activities require a very high level of prior knowledge and skills (e.g., attendance at university in later life; see Patterson et al., 2016), or tend to be the result of a lifelong involvement in similar activities (e.g., engagement in political organizations; see Jennings et al., 1990). By contrast, other activities, such as the majority of leisure options offered by civic or senior centers, are less demanding and therefore accessible to more people (Bobitt, 2016).

According to these two axes (self- and other-orientation, and high and low levels of resources), active aging activities can be classified into four types: self-oriented activities involving a low level of resources (e.g., most leisure activities offered by senior centers), self-oriented activities involving a high level of resources (e.g., attendance at a University of the Third Age), other-oriented activities involving a low level of resources (e.g., voluntary activities that do not require previous experience) and other-oriented activities involving a high level of resources (e.g., political activism) (Villar, Celdrán, Serrat, & Cannella, 2018).

Active aging and learning

It is reasonable to think that older people acquire some kind of learning as a result of their involvement in active aging activities. Thus, even though learning can also be viewed as a process, this study focuses on learning outcomes, defined as any kind of personal change, in terms of knowledge, skills or attitudes, which people perceive as resulting from their participation in a certain activity irrespective of its nature (e.g., activities with explicit educational aims, such as formal or non-formal educational activities, or without these aims). In the context of the issues addressed in this study, learning outcomes may be crucial to understand the benefits of being involved in active aging activities and why older people maintain their commitment to the activity regardless of costs, in terms of time and effort and regardless of the possible drawbacks that the activity may also involve (Wilson et al., 2006).

In the case of activities that take place in formal and non-formal educational contexts, learning outcomes may match the explicit educational aims of the activities in question, but this is not necessarily the case. In addition, other activities without any explicit educational aim may also involve some kind of learning outcome. This kind of learning beyond any explicit educational aim has been labeled “informal” or “experiential”. For instance, Schugurensky & Myers (2008, p. 75), defined informal learning as “...the body of

knowledge, skills, attitudes, perspectives and values acquired outside of the curricula of educational institutions (formal education) and outside of the programmes and workshops offered by a variety of social agencies (non-formal education)". Even if this kind of learning is not pursued intentionally, if people are explicitly asked about what they have learned from their involvement in a certain activity, they are generally able to reflect and retrospectively identify it as a learning outcome (Serrat, Petriwskyj, Villar, & Warburton, 2016).

Consequently, it is important to underline that informal learning also takes place both in everyday, social and community activities and in formal and non-formal educational institutions and contexts. In this case, learning outcomes may be independent of the objectives pursued by the curricula of these institutions: they sometimes correspond to formal or non-formal educational objectives, while in other cases they are unexpected or, in extreme cases, may even conflict with the intended goals (Schugurensky, 2000).

Some studies, not specifically focused on older people, have explored learning outcomes from participation in community organizations. For instance, Ilsey (1990) took a sample of volunteers and found three types of learning outcomes: (a) instrumental learning, which is related to acquiring the skills necessary for voluntary work; (b) social learning, which is linked to communication, respect, compassion and openness, and (c) critical thinking, which is associated with a reflection on personal and societal values and priorities. More recently, Belda-Miquel, Boni-Aristizábal, and Sañudo-Pazos (2016) used samples that included a wider range of civic organizations and found similar results in terms of learning outcomes, including instrumental skills, social competences and a broader understanding of the community and society as a whole.

Despite the recent interest in promoting active aging and older people's participation, research on learning outcomes involving older samples remains scarce. The few studies published suggest that older people who participate in voluntary work (Chen, 2016a, 2016b),

leisure activities (MacKean & Abbott-Chapman, 2011), educational activities (Lee, 2016) and political organizations (Schugurensky & Myers, 2008; Serrat et al., 2016) reported some learning outcomes from participation, ranging from specific and instrumental skills, such as how to use computers and communicate more effectively with others, to other, more comprehensive and psychological benefits, including increased self-awareness, self-confidence, empowerment and spiritual growth.

Despite this, no studies have so far systematically compared learning outcomes in samples of older people who participate in different activity types. Furthermore, most studies on learning outcomes have focused on specific activities such as volunteering, while other popular active aging activities (e.g., leisure and participation in educational programs) have been subject to far less research. In that respect, the classification proposed above could provide a starting point to compare different experiences of active aging in terms of learning outcomes. This knowledge could be key to understanding the differentiating factors that determine whether people remain involved in an activity and to improve the experiences of older people who participate in different active aging activities

In light of the above, the aim of the study was to explore and compare learning outcomes acquired from different active aging activities (leisure activities, university studies, volunteering and political activism). To do so, three research questions were raised:

RQ1: What do older people learn from their participation in active aging activities?

RQ2: Do learning outcomes differ according to the active aging activity, and particularly, to its orientation (self- vs other-oriented) and level of resources (high vs low) involved?

RQ3: Are learning outcomes associated with sociodemographic variables such as gender, educational level or income?

Method

Participants

An intentional sample of 448 people aged 60 years and above volunteered to participate in the study. At the time of the study they were involved in one of the following four types of active aging activities: leisure activities (112 participants), study at a University of the Third Age (113), volunteering (133), and active involvement in a political organizations (90). Each activity represents one of the four types of active aging activities described previously according to our two axes of self- and other-orientation and high and low levels of resources.

Participants' average age was 70.1 years ($SD = 7.3$), and 57.4% of the sample were female. Most participants in the study were married (64.0). As for education level, close to a third (32.5%) reported having primary (or lower) education, a third (33.3%) secondary education and the last third (34.2%) had completed university studies. Table 1 shows the profile of the subsamples in terms of sociodemographic and participatory variables, as well as the statistical significance of the differences.

INSERT TABLE 1

As well as involvement in a formal organization promoting one of the four active aging activities mentioned, participants were required to meet the following inclusion criteria: (a) Being 60 years of age or above; (b) Being retired; (c) Spending at least one hour a week on the target activity; and (d) Having participated in the target activity for at least one year.

We received 475 completed questionnaires. In order to be able to carry out the analysis in groups that were as homogenous as possible, we excluded older people who were

involved in more than one formal organization or in more than one of the activities considered in the study. For this reason, questionnaires from 27 participants were excluded and the final sample comprised 448 older people.

Instruments

The participants answered a self-administered questionnaire specifically developed by the authors for the purposes of this study. It comprised two sections; section one elicited sociodemographic information, including age, gender, marital status (single, married/living in a couple, widowed, divorced/separated), education level (with four options: ‘no education,’ ‘primary education,’ ‘secondary education’ and ‘university education’), and income level (‘<500,’ ‘500-999,’ ‘1000-1499,’ ‘1500-1999’ and ‘>2000’ euros per month). Participants were also required to answer three questions relating to the activity for which they were selected: how many years they had been involved in the activity, how many hours they devoted to it each week and how important it was in their life (on a scale of 1, i.e., ‘not important at all,’ to 10, i.e., ‘extremely important’).

The second section of the questionnaire included open, open-ended and standardized instruments in relation to the activity, their life and their social connections. Due to the scarcity of research on learning and active aging activities, we chose an exploratory approach that used an open question to determine the participants’ opinions in their own words. The results reported in this study correspond to the questions regarding learning obtained as a result of their participation in their active aging activity. Specifically, answers to two questions were analyzed:

- a. Do you think you have learned something valuable from your participation in this activity? (possible answers were ‘Yes,’ ‘No’ and ‘Don’t know’)

b. If so, could you briefly describe what you have mainly learned?

In this second question, there was no restriction on the number of ideas (or learning outcomes) participants could record. Most participants reported just one learning outcome, but 12 of them mentioned two and two participants mentioned three. Consequently, the 448 participants produced 477 learning outcomes.

Procedure

Four subsamples were included in our study, each one recruited from different organizations, according to the typology of active aging activities described in the introduction and intentionally chosen. All of them were located in Barcelona, Spain.

For the self-oriented/low level of resources profile, older people involved in leisure activities organized by community centers were selected. These centers are sponsored by the city council and their aim is to provide leisure and social activities for older people. Participation in these activities is generally free and they do not require a previous level of expertise or a regular or an intense level of involvement. The activities were card games, arts and crafts or dancing.

For the self-oriented, high level of resources profile, we selected participants attending the University of the Third Age. These participants follow a specific curriculum and schedule of classes within a two-year academic degree, organized by the University of Barcelona. Participants were recruited from the first-course students on the degrees of Arts, Sciences and Psychology.

The other-oriented, high level of resources profile comprised older participants in political parties and trade unions based in Barcelona. These political activists were usually

more committed in terms of time devoted to their activity, and tended to have been involved in politics at earlier times in their lives (Serrat & Villar, 2019).

Finally, for the other-oriented and low level of resources profile, older volunteers involved in a non-governmental organization located also in Barcelona were selected. The organization in question was focused on lonely people. Volunteers helped by supporting the organization's users in daily life activities (e.g. accompanying them to the doctor or buying groceries) and offering company and conversation. Volunteers' involvement was generally less intense than in the case of political activists.

The process of recruitment followed two steps in all the cases. Firstly, we contacted the director of the organization, outlining the procedures and the aims of the research and asking them for help in recruiting participants. Virtually all older people approached agreed to participate in the study; the ones who declined (no more than 10-12 people) said that they lacked time. Secondly, once contacted, participants received a written document informing them about the study's objectives and the data collection procedure and instructing them how to complete the questionnaire. The document also contained information on confidentiality, the preservation of anonymity, and their right not to answer and to abandon the study at any time. All participants gave explicit written consent before completing the questionnaire. The study was approved by the XXXX's Ethics Committee.

Once the results were available, the authors gave the directors of the participant organizations a report summarizing the results and indicating how their specific organization compared with the rest.

Data analysis

To identify the learning outcomes reported by participants after their engagements in an active aging activity, the answers they gave were subjected to content analysis. This analysis consisted of four steps. First, we isolated the ideas or units of meaning in each participant's answer. Second, we condensed these ideas into first- and second-order categories, according to repetitions or similarities in meaning. To enhance the validity of the results, this process was carried out independently by two researchers (the second and fourth authors), who subsequently compared their category systems and discussed the differences until they reached a consensus. Third, these two researchers used the resulting category system to re-categorize all the units of meaning. Finally, a researcher who had not been involved in the development of the category system (the third author) categorized a randomly selected section (around 30%) of units of meaning in accordance with the final version of the system. Her categorization and the initial categorization were compared to calculate the kappa index of interobserver agreement. This index was found to be .88, which suggested that the category system was very reliable.

After obtaining the final version of the categories, chi-square tests were performed to cross the categories with the active aging activities (leisure, university study, volunteering and political activism).

Finally, we wanted to explore the predictive value of certain socio-demographic variables (age, gender, education and income) in the main categories, as well as ascertain whether the addition of these variables would modify the influence of the type of active aging activity. To do so, we performed four binomial multivariable logistic regressions, one for each learning category. All quantitative analyses were performed using the SPSS statistical package version 25.

Results

The vast majority of the participants (97.5%) stated that they had learned something valuable from their involvement in the active aging activity.

From answers to the open question “could you briefly describe what you have mainly learned?” 477 units or ideas were extracted, as some participants provided more than one idea to complete this question. Those units were organized within two first-order response categories: self-focused learning and other-focused learning. Within each category, two second-order categories emerged (see Table 2). A minority of participants (4.5%) gave an answer that did not fit into the first-order categories (e.g., “many, many things,” woman, 71, student; and “not that much, I’m a bit depressed at the moment,” man, 76, leisure participant).

INSERT TABLE 2

What participants learned from the activities?

Responses were distributed in two main first-order categories: self-focused learning (mentioned by 49.9% of the participants) and other-focused learning (mentioned by 50.4% of the participants).

Self-focused learning. Self-focused learning included answers that expressed having learned something with a clearly personal orientation, that is, the individuals themselves benefited from participation in the active aging activity. This category of self-focused learning was divided into two subcategories, one related to self-knowledge and the other to the acquisition of instrumental skills.

Learning associated with Instrumental Skills was mentioned by 33.3% of the participants. This refers to the acquisition of new knowledge, skills or competences as a result

of involvement in the active aging activity. For instance, a woman who participated in a dance workshop mentioned that she had learned “new rhythms, new techniques” (woman, 72, leisure participant), while a university student expressed that she had learned “about how the mind and brain work” (woman, 66, student). Other participants mentioned that they had learned aspects relating to new technologies and computers. Thus, a 78-year-old woman expressed that she had learned “not to be afraid of computers and to be able to use them” (woman, volunteer). Finally, participation was also considered as a space to acquire or relearn prior knowledge: “To update my knowledge and refresh my rusty knowledge” (woman, 65, student).

The second self-focused subcategory was called ‘Knowing Oneself’ and was mentioned by 17.9% of the participants. In contrast to Instrumental Skills, this second type of learning was far more general and less closely related to the activity carried out by participants. It reflected their capacity to understand and value themselves, and included aspects such as improving management of their emotions, experiencing feelings of usefulness and personal worth, changing or reinforcing personal values and even reformulating their life philosophy as a result of their involvement in the active aging activity. Thus, some participants reported that they had learned about themselves and how to handle their emotions better. A volunteer said that she had learned to “understand my attitudes and reactions better” (woman, 79 years, volunteer). With regard to the second aspect, a woman studying at a University of the Third Age said, “It has helped me learn more about myself, to understand my feelings and not to attach importance to irrelevant things. I see life in a more positive light now” (woman, 61, student).

Other participants revealed that their participation in active aging activities had helped increase their confidence and self-worth. For instance, a student mentioned that she had learned “to have more self-esteem and believe in myself” (woman, 66, student). Moreover,

participation in and contact with different realities helped some participants redefine or reinforce certain attitudes and personal values. Thus, an activist stated that she had learned “to have more patience and be more compassionate” (woman, 84, activist), and a volunteer said he had learned “to be more tolerant” (man, 72, activist). Finally, learning related to self-knowledge reflected a new approach to life and a shift in priorities, as one participant mentioned: “To value all the good things in my life and not pay so much attention to the negative side of life” (woman, 76, leisure participant).

Other-focused learning. Other-focused learning included answers in which learning as a result of participation in active aging activities reflected a benefit that extended beyond the participants themselves and involved others and how the participants related to them, either in specific terms (how participants related to and understood other people) or in more abstract and general terms (how participants related to and understood their community or society). Two subcategories were identified within this category: one related to the acquisition of interpersonal knowledge and the other concerning social or community knowledge.

Learning associated with Interpersonal Knowledge was mentioned by 37.3% of the participants. These answers reflected the reformulation of relationships with other people and included an increase in social networks, aspects related to the quality of relationships and the development of a wider and more in-depth understanding of others.

Thus, some participants mentioned that their relationships improved as a result of their participation in active aging activities. For instance, one volunteer said that participating led to him having “more and better relationships with others” (man, 67, volunteer). Another participant reported that he had learned “to live together, to understand other people and to enjoy giving more” (man, 65, activist). Contact with others allowed some participants to

acquire communication skills, a result reflected in the answer of this older activist: “I’ve learned how to talk to people” (woman, 81, activist). Another participant stated that she had developed her oral skills: “I’ve learned how to speak and deal with people in public” (woman, 66, activist).

Being involved in active aging activities also helped participants learn about the importance of team and collaborative work, as highlighted by these participants: “How to work with other people and how to collaborate with people from different backgrounds” (woman, 68, activist) and “How to work in small groups” (man, 67, student). This subcategory also reflected an appreciation of issues such as diversity. For some participants, being involved in active aging activities had led to an appreciation of the importance of considering and truly understanding others’ opinions. For instance, one participant said, “To understand other people, be able to put myself in their shoes” (woman, 62, volunteer), and another said, “To understand and deal with different people, and to get to know them better” (man, 71, volunteer).

The second subcategory, mentioned by 12.6% of participants, was called Social Knowledge. It alluded to two different aspects: firstly, to learning about community values, including solidarity and altruism, and secondly, to more abstract learning about how the social system or society as a whole works. In the first case, one participant said that participating enabled him to understand “that solidarity is a never-ending goal” (man, 77, activist). This view was reflected in another answer, provided by a student, who linked solidarity with a reduction in inequality: “To work for others, in solidarity with others, so that inequalities lessen” (man, 65). In the second case, activity was viewed as a tool to prompt social change, and the answers reflected an implicit knowledge about society, as expressed in the following response from an activist: “To show solidarity, after realizing that today’s society is broken and that we should push for change” (man, 65). Another participant said,

“We are social beings and we live better, get more done and transmit values more effectively as a group” (man, 66, activist).

Relationships with the type of activity

Six chi-square tests were performed to compare whether mention frequencies for each first- and second-order categories differed according to active aging activity. **In all chi-squares, we crossed the presence of the category (yes or not) by the four types of activity.** Results yielded statistically significant relationships for all categories (see Table 2).

Participants in leisure activities and in the University of the Third Age tended to mention Self-focused learning more often than volunteers and particularly activists ($\chi^2(3) = 56.08, p < 0.001$). Such differences arose mainly from the Instrumental Skills category, which was far more frequent among the leisure participants and students than the volunteers and activists ($\chi^2(3) = 50.13, p < 0.001$). By contrast, the differences in Knowing Oneself were not so great. The group that mentioned this subcategory most frequently was students, followed by volunteers and leisure participants ($\chi^2(3) = 10.74, p = 0.013$).

In the case of Other-focused learning, the pattern was exactly the opposite: volunteers and activists mentioned this category far more often than leisure participants and older students ($\chi^2(3) = 66.54, p < 0.001$). Such differences also appeared in both second-order categories (Interpersonal Knowledge and Social Knowledge; $\chi^2(3) = 11.85, p = 0.008$ and $\chi^2(3) = 94.63, p < 0.001$ respectively). Of particular note was the fact that almost half the activists mentioned Social Knowledge as a type of learning acquired from participation in their activity, while this category was scarcely present in the other groups, particularly among leisure participants and older students.

Relationships with socio-demographic variables

In order to explore the influence of socio-demographic variables (age, gender, education and income) on types of learning outcomes, we performed one binomial logistic regressions for each of the four second-order learning categories, **taking these categories as dichotomic variables (yes if the participant did mention the category, no if not)** (see Table 3). Socio-demographic variables were not significantly associated with Self-focused learnings: age showed a small, but statistically significant, relationship with Social Relationships (Wald $\chi^2(1) = 3.91, p = 0.048$; the older the participant, the less probability the category would be mentioned) and education was related to Social Knowledge (Wald $\chi^2(2) = 8.79, p = 0.012$), a category that was mentioned more by the more educated participants (secondary or university education) than those with primary studies or less.

INSERT TABLE 3

As the type of activity also entered into the regressions, some of the relationships between type of activity and type of learning that appeared in the bivariate analyses disappeared in multivariable analyses. Specifically, Instrumental Learning was more frequent among leisure and university participants than among volunteers and activists (Wald $X^2(3) = 39.79, p < 0.001$), while the opposite was true for Social Knowledge (Wald $X^2(3) = 50.94, p < 0.001$). Self-Knowledge and Social Relations did not present significant differences with regard to the type of active aging activity.

Discussion

The aims of the study was to determine what types of learning were acquired by people as a result of their participation in active aging activities (RQ1). We also wanted to compare these learning outcomes across the different activities (RQ2) and explore their association with socio-demographic variables (RQ3).

The results showed that regardless of what was specifically learned, older people were able to mention important learning types as a result of their participation in a variety of active aging activities. As for the first research question, these learning types were relatively diverse and were not restricted to self-oriented aspects, but also included aspects that involved others. Participants mentioned the acquisition of skills and learning new ways of doing things, but they also expressed aspects more associated with knowledge and even with attitudes, and highlighted new ways of understanding, approaching and prioritizing things.

Our results support Schugurensky's view of the lack of overlap between the explicit or implicit learning objectives of different active aging activities and what participants actually learned from the activity (Schugurensky, 2000). Correspondence between the two aspects of learning was sometimes found (e.g., in Instrumental Skills) and was particularly high when the activity was defined by its explicitly educational nature (e.g., University of the Third Age), but it was by no means the dominant feature. Participants in active aging activities seemed to view the activities as a learning experience that goes far beyond any formal educational objective, and were able to draw lessons that they consider important to their own life.

These 'life lessons' may, in turn, be key to understanding their involvement in the activity. While previous research has underlined the positive impacts associated with participation in active aging activities, ranging from health to psychological and social benefits (Marsillas et al., 2017), learning may be an essential link to explain how these benefits are achieved. For instance, some types of social learning (e.g., an increase in interpersonal knowledge) mentioned by our participants may directly help to broaden and enrich their social networks. In a similar way, learning in relation to self- or social knowledge may play a role in the psychological benefits provided by an active lifestyle in later life. This suggests a reinforcing and circular relationship between learning outcomes and active aging.

This relationship was already noted by Chen (2016a, 2016b) in older volunteers, and our study actually extends it to other types of active aging activities.

In addition, knowing the learning types associated with active aging activities leads to a better understanding of the meaning of these activities for older people and the reasons underlying their involvement and their interest in continuing their participation. Taken together, our results highlight the importance of focusing on the experience of participating. This aspect has been largely overlooked by previous research, which has focused more on the predictors (e.g., Principi et al., 2016) and outcomes (Bertozzi et al., 2017) of participation.

However, as expected, the nature of learning depended on the type of activity. This was the starting-point for our second research question. Even though participants learned something from all activities, the nature and depth of learning seemed to be diverse. When analyzing the bivariate associations between learning and activities, therefore, the difference between self-oriented and other-oriented active aging activities seemed to be confirmed in terms of the learning acquired. Thus, while participants in self-oriented activities such as leisure activities and studying at the University of the Third Age tended to mention self-oriented learning as well, those who participated in other-oriented activities such as volunteering and political activism were more likely to mention learning with a social dimension.

Within each type of activity, a multivariate analysis yielded differences. In the case of self-oriented activities, both participants at the University of the Third Age and participants in leisure activities mentioned more learning associated with instrumental skills. With respect to other-oriented activities, learning related to a deeper understanding of society and its institutions was mentioned more frequently by volunteers and, particularly, by political activists than by university students or participants in leisure activities. Thus, the very nature

of the activity seems to be the key factor that determines the learning type acquired. Our results demonstrate that, although it is possible to learn something from all active aging activities, not every activity seems to have the same value and potential in terms of learning, and that the orientation of the activity (self- vs other-oriented) is more relevant than the potential amount of resources needed to perform it (low vs high resources). While self-oriented activities favor more instrumental, specific learning closely linked to the explicit activity at stake, other-oriented activities are likely to promote more abstract learning, which may deepen the participant's understanding of the social forces operating in their community and in society as a whole.

As for the impact of sociodemographic variables, none of them seemed to influence learning outcomes related to Self-knowledge, Instrumental skills or Social Relationships. However, the more educated a person, the more she or he is likely to identify social knowledge as an outcome, which suggest that achieving the abstract, deep understanding of society involved in the category Social Knowledge is facilitated by having a certain level of education.

Any interpretation of these results should take account of the study's limitations. First, it was conducted with intentionally gathered samples, so they can by no means be considered as representative of all older people who participate in the different activities included in the study. Second, only four activities were explored in the study, while of course the number of potential active aging activities is far higher; thus, many more learning types might have been identified if other activities had been included. In addition, all the activities were formally organized. Although this latter feature facilitates comparisons between subsamples, people who do not participate in associations or are involved in activities by themselves might have identified different learning outcomes. In addition, using self-report data, gathered by means of a single open question that provided just a limited space to answer, is likely to restrict the

type and number of learning outcomes mentioned by participants. Future research including alternative methodological approaches to assess learning outcomes (both quantitatively and qualitatively) would help to enrich and triangulate the results yielded by this preliminary study. Finally, the study was focused on learning understood as an outcome, identified at a particular moment in time as a result of the activity in question. Obviously, learning can also be seen as a process, and using this dynamic approach might give different results. Therefore, further studies comparing learning outcomes and learning processes would be a welcome addition to the literature on learning from active aging activities.

Despite these limitations, our research represents a valuable contribution to the literature on active aging by highlighting the problem of referring to active aging as a single and homogenous form of successful aging. Considering active aging in a generic way masks the fact that the qualifier “active” conceals a wide range of activities that may share few similarities and may have a diverse impact on people, not just in terms of health-related, psychological and social outcomes, but also, as our results show, in terms of the experience of participating in and learning from the activity. This diversity is key to designing better-tailored interventions aimed at involving more older people in active forms of aging and ensuring that older people remain engaged in the activities in which they take part.

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Table 1. Comparative profile of older people engaged in active aging activities, by type of activity

Variables	Leisure (n=112)	University (n=113)	Volunteering (n=133)	Political (n=90)	Total (N=448)
Gender (%) ***					
Male	23.0	31.6	52.3	67.0	42.7
Female	77.0	68.4	47.7	33.0	57.3
Marital status (%) **					
Married	52.1	66.5	70.5	67.3	64.4
Widow	32.7	15.8	9.8	15.0	17.9
Other	15.2	17.7	19.7	17.7	17.7
Age, <i>M (SD)</i> , years***	72.6 (7.2)	64.8 (5.4)	70.9 (7.4)	70.9 (6.2)	70.1 (7.3)
Studies (%) ***					
Primary studies or less	67.3	9.6	20.8	26.1	30.8
Secondary	18.6	39.5	35.4	42.0	33.5
University	14.2	50.9	43.8	31.8	35.7
Income (euros/month), (%) ***					
Less than 500	12.6	0.9	2.3	0	3.9
500-900	44.7	6.3	15.5	10.2	19.0
1000-1499	25.2	14.4	27.1	27.3	23.4

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1500-1999	12.6	35.1	27.9	27.3	26.0
2000 or more	4.9	43.2	27.1	35.2	27.6
Years participating <i>M (SD)</i> , ***	6.3 (5.9)	3.2 (4.2)	8.5 (8.3)	18.9 (17.5)	8.5 (10.7)
Hours committed per week <i>M (SD)</i> ***	5.5 (4.2)	6.7 (3.8)	9.9 (8.6)	12.9 (11.4)	8.3 (7.6)

Note: p values are based on the χ^2 statistic or *F* statistic, according to the nature of the variable *** $p < .001$. ** $p < .01$

Table 2. Frequencies and percentages (among brackets) of learning, comparing by active aging activities

Category	Active aging activity				
	Leisure (n=112)	University (n=113)	Volunteerism (n=133)	Political (n=90)	Total (N= 448)
Self-focused learning ***	74 (66.1)	83 (73.5)	55 (41.3)	15 (16.7)	227 (50.7)
Instrumental skills ***	57 (50.9)	56 (49.6)	28 (21.1)	8 (8.9)	149 (33.3)
Knowing oneself *	19 (17.0)	28 (24.8)	26 (19.5)	7 (7.8)	80 (17.9)
Other-focused learning ***	37 (33.0)	37 (32.7)	86 (64.7)	66 (73.3)	226 (50.4)
Interpersonal Knowledge **	36 (32.1)	33 (29.2)	64 (48.1)	34 (37.8)	167 (37.3)
Social Knowledge***	2 (1.8)	4 (3.5)	21 (15.8)	39 (43.3)	66 (14.7)
Others	6 (5.4)	6 (5.3)	6 (4.5)	2 (2.2)	20 (4.5)

Note: p values are based on the χ^2 statistic

*** $p < .001$. ** $p < .01$ * $p < .05$

Table 3. Logistic regression models predicting learnings from participation in active aging activities (N = 448)

Categories	Type of learning			
	Self-Knowledge	Instrumental	Social Relations	Social Knowledge
	<i>OR [95% CI]</i>	<i>OR [95% CI]</i>	<i>OR [95% CI]</i>	<i>OR [95% CI]</i>
Age	0.99 [0.95-1.04]	1.01[0.98-1.05]	0.96* [0.93-1.00]	1.02 [0.96-1.07]
Gender (Male = 0)				
Female	0.72 [0.39-1.27]	1.19 [0.74-1.91]	0.85 [0.55-1.32]	0.73 [0.58-2.09]
Education (Primary studies or less = 0)				
Secondary education	1.36 [0.63-2.93]	0.79 [0.42-1.46]	0.93 [0.53-1.62]	3.60** [1.52-8.56]
University education	1.53 [0.66-3.54]	1.49 [0.58-2.25]	0.98 [0.53-1.80]	3.19* [0.99-5.73]
Income (\leq 1000 euros = 0)				
1001-1500 euros	1.65 [0.74-3.67]	1.41 [0.72-2.74]	1.55 [0.83-2.96]	1.17 [0.43-3.15]
\geq 1501 euros	0.96 [0.38-2.43]	1.66 [0.78-3.51]	1.34 [0.66-2.71]	.99 [0.34-2.85]
Type of activity (Leisure = 0)				
\geq 1501 euros	0.86 [0.33-2.23]	1.27 [0.57-2.83]	1.74 [0.84-3.59]	1.09 [0.38-3.20]

University	1.57 [0.63-3.91]	1.28 [0.63-2.62]	0.72 [0.34-1.50]	1.68 [0.27-10.29]
Volunteering	1.41 [0.63-3.145]	0.30*** [0.15-0.59]	1.63 [0.87-3.03]	7.42** [1.60-34.37]
Political	0.43 [0.14-1.34]	0.14*** [0.06-0.34]	1.56 [0.78-3.09]	35.71*** [7.75-164.37]
Model sum. χ^2 (<i>df</i> , <i>p</i> value)	16.67 (10, <.082)	52.28 (10, <.000)	18.29 (10, <.050)	93.10 (15, <.000)
Log likelihood	365.92	499.31	5628.87	286.12
Nagelkerke's R^2	.062	.152	.054	0.324

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$